

Retail Store Sales Prediction using Machine Learning

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Abstract — It's critical for businesses to forecast their present revenue. By using prediction, business owners can make the right decisions for their upcoming sales. A comparative study of two Machine Learning algorithm, Linear Regression and Multilinear Regression are done in this paper. A class of methods known as "machine learning" enables software programmes to predict outcomes more accurately without having to be explicitly coded. Machine learning's central tenet is the development of models and the application of algorithms that can take input data and, through statistical analysis, predict an output while updating outputs as new data becomes available. These models are adaptable to a variety of situations and may be trained to fulfil management requirements so that exact actions can be taken to achieve the organization's objective. The model is created using machine learning techniques and the dataset. Machine learning algorithms assess the model's accuracy by examining the data.

Keywords— Machine learning, Simple Linear Regression, Multiple Linear Regression, Sales Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the crucial aspects of a business's operations is the sale. Sales fluctuate for a variety of causes, including retail locations, services, and products. Merchants who operate many stores must individually track each store's sales in order to respond appropriately to the store that is performing poorly.

The geographic location of stores has a significant impact on their sales. The earning potential of a store located in a city is greater than that of a store located in an urban region. Therefore, depending on these characteristics, each store must adopt a unique strategy to enhance their sales. We anticipate the sales of each shop in this model using ML, and we also assess the model's accuracy. Business owners can use prediction to pinpoint the locations that are making less money and take the appropriate action to fix the problem. In terms of sales and market share, e-commerce companies like Amazon and Flipkart have had significant development in recent years. On the other hand, due in part to a lack of technology resources, small firms, sometimes referred to as Medium, Small, and Micro Enterprises (MSMEs), have found it challenging to compete with major merchants. Forecasting sales is a challenging but essential responsibility in revitalising MSMEs' growth strategy since it helps them make sensible strategic decisions. Businesses can better manage their inventories, cash flows, and resources by optimising their supply chains. The effectiveness of a model's sales prediction determines the value of sales forecasting.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the paper [1], market basket analysis creates a frequent item set, or association rules, that can easily reveal client purchasing patterns. The merchant can set up his retail store with the aid of these principles and grow his business in the future. The Apriori algorithm is the primary algorithm used in market basket analysis. It can be a very effective technique for analysing customer purchase trends.

They constructed and evaluated numerous models in the research [2] to address a problem that these small enterprises face: forecasting sales. This enables companies to make more strategic decisions about investments, supply chain management, and inventory management. The researcher was able to focus on four commonly used regression approaches in order to forecast future sales.

In the paper [3], they use a predictive model that makes use of the Xgboost technique to forecast the sales of a business similar to Big Mart and find that the model performs better than other models. The model is thoroughly compared to other models in terms of performance indicators.

III. MOTIVATION

Merchants need the information about their stores for maintaining the market. If they can achieve the information through online it will save them a lot of time. Website can provide information more quickly and accurately based on algorithm it is used. The proposed system will calculate the total sales of each store and using that information the merchants can react to the changes that occur to each store quickly.

IV. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The goal of this study is to develop a machine learning model that accurately predicts the sales of each store from the provided dataset. It helps the merchants to create more accurate decisions about which store they need to concentrate more and which one has the highest sales. The training and testing data sets are created from the dataset. For the model to learn accurately, more data should be used during training. A sales prediction model can be made using the model's output. To predict the sales, the Simple Linear Regression and Multiple Linear Regression algorithms will be employed. The organisation is:

Fig.1:Sales Prediction System Methodology

The tasks that must be taken are:

- A. Data Collection
- B. Data Pre-processing
- C. Model Building
- D. Result

A. Data Collection:

We employed a structured format for the dataset in this system. The dataset being used includes sales of each item in relation to its stores. A training dataset and a testing dataset were created from the dataset. Our machine learning algorithms were all trained on the training datasets that we used to create our models. Finally, we included a testing dataset for you to evaluate the precision of this trained model.

B. Data Pre-processing:

This step is the beginning of every machine learning technique. This process includes data transformation, data cleaning, and data minimization. Some activities are made to improve the effectiveness of the data. To ensure that the categorization is accurate, we can process the data to increase the model's accuracy.

C. Machine Learning:

To forecast sales, this is employed. In order to check the current condition of stores, machine learning techniques are employed to predict sales of each store. To find the sales, various classifiers are available. The accuracy of the

classifier depends on how it was trained. High accuracy should be required of classifiers.

1. Simple Linear Regression:

A linear regression model called simple linear regression in statistics has only one explanatory variable. In other words, it searches for a linear function that, as precisely as feasible, predicts the values of the dependent variable as a function of the independent variable for two-dimensional sample points with one independent variable and one dependent variable. The term "simple" describes the relationship between the result variable and a single predictor. The dependant variable for simple linear regression must have a continuous or real value. The independent variable, however, can be quantified using either continuous or categorical values.

2. Multiple Linear Regression:

A statistical method known as multiple linear regression is used to forecast the result of a variable based on the values of two or more additional variables. This development of linear regression is known as multiple regression. Independent or explanatory variables are the factors we use to make predictions about the value of the dependent variable, whereas the dependent variable is the actual variable.

V. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the retail shop sales prediction. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```

# necessary imports
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import pickle

import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')

sns.set()
%matplotlib inline
    
```

2. Add the dataset into jupyter.

```

In [5]: data = pd.read_csv('Sales.csv') # Loading the data
    
```

```

In [6]: data.head()
    
```

```

Out[6]:
    
```

	Unnamed: 0	Shop_A	Shop_B	Shop_C	sales
0	1	230.1	37.8	69.2	22.1
1	2	44.5	39.3	45.1	10.4
2	3	17.2	45.9	69.3	9.3
3	4	151.5	41.3	58.5	18.5
4	5	180.8	10.8	58.4	12.9

3. Then split the dataset into training and testing datasets.

```

In [18]: # splitting data into training and testing data
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size = 0.25, random_state = 0)
X_train.shape, y_train.shape, X_test.shape, y_test.shape

Out[18]: ((150, 1), (150,), (50, 1), (50,))
    
```

4. Creating scatterplot to find the shop that has highest sales.

```

In [13]: # visualizing the relationship between the features and the label
fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize = (21, 7), sharey = True)
sns.scatterplot(x = 'Shop_A', y = 'sales', data = data, ax = ax[0])
sns.scatterplot(x = 'Shop_B', y = 'sales', data = data, ax = ax[1])
sns.scatterplot(x = 'Shop_C', y = 'sales', data = data, ax = ax[2])
plt.show()
    
```

5. Finding the accuracy of the models.

Simple Linear Regression:

```
In [22]: # accuracy of model
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, mean_absolute_error
from math import sqrt
print(f"Mean Squared Error of Model is : {mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)}")
print(f"Mean Absolute Error of Model is : {mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred)}")
print(f"Root Mean Squared Error of Model is : {sqrt(mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred))}")
Mean Squared Error of Model is : 8.730248872947453
Mean Absolute Error of Model is : 2.298513328039085
Root Mean Squared Error of Model is : 2.954699455604149
```

Multiple Linear Regression:

```
In [140]: # accuracy of model
print(f"Mean Squared Error of Model is : {mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)}")
print(f"Mean Absolute Error of Model is : {mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred)}")
print(f"Root Mean Squared Error of Model is : {sqrt(mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred))}")
Mean Squared Error of Model is : 3.9998526675817487
Mean Absolute Error of Model is : 1.2947484377946767
Root Mean Squared Error of Model is : 1.9999631665562616
```

VI. RESULTS

Using dataset, two machine learning methods were employed, and the outcomes for each methodology were slightly varied due to the distinct working criteria of each algorithm. The results were evaluated on the basis of accuracy

Method	Accuracy	
	Training	Testing
Simple Linear Regression	0.576	0.690
Multiple Linear Regression	0.907	0.858

VII. CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study is to forecast the sales of each shop and find a suitable machine learning algorithm for more accuracy. We can find the shop that has best sales using scatterplot and using that data we can determine the accuracy of the models. Future reference is that using more complex algorithm you can increase the accuracy of the prediction.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] "Sales Prediction of Market using Machine Learning" Soham Patangia , Madhura Mokashi, Kevin Shah.
- [2] "Predicting E-commerce Sales & Inventory Management using Machine Learning" Divyansh Agnani, Abhishek Bavkar, Samarth Salgar
- [3] "A Comparative Study of Big Mart Sales Prediction" Gopal Behera and Neeta Nain